

Comprehensive Design and Analysis of a Prosthetic Leg: Material Selection and Performance Evaluation

K. Ramanjan¹, K. Rakesh², Dr A. Jawahar Babu³

¹ Student of Mechanical Engineering, SR Gudlavalleru Engineering College, Gudlavalleru, 20481A0378@qecgudlavallerumic.in

² Student of Mechanical Engineering, SR Gudlavalleru Engineering College, Gudlavalleru, 20481A0363@qecgudlavallerumic.in

³ Professor of Mechanical Engineering, SR Gudlavalleru Engineering College, Gudlavalleru, ajbsrgec@gmail.com

Author for correspondence: Dr A Jawahar Babu, Professor of Mechanical Engineering, SR Gudlavalleru Engineering College, Gudlavalleru, 9440692472, ajbsrgec@gmail.com

Abstract

Prosthetic limbs serve as indispensable tools in restoring mobility and enhancing the quality of life for individuals with limb loss. This project focuses on the modeling and analysis of prosthetic legs, aiming to optimize their design for improved functionality and comfort. The study begins with an exploration of the significance of prostheses in enhancing the mobility and independence of amputees. Utilizing Solid Works for modeling and ANSYS for analysis, the project investigates the performance of prosthetic legs constructed from four distinct materials: Aluminum Alloy, Titanium Alloy, Carbon Fibre, and Structural Steel. These materials are selected based on their mechanical properties and suitability for prosthetic applications. The design and analysis stages involve simulating various activities that mimic the typical movements and stresses encountered during daily life, including walking and engaging in other essential tasks. By subjecting the prosthetic leg models to rigorous testing, the project evaluates their durability, strength, and overall performance under realistic conditions. The outcomes of this research provide valuable insights into the comparative advantages and limitations of different materials in prosthetic leg design. Additionally, it offers recommendations for optimizing prosthetic limb design to better meet the diverse needs and preferences of users. Ultimately, this work contributes to advancing the field of prosthetic engineering, paving the way for the development of more efficient and user-friendly prosthetic solutions.

Key words: Prosthetic leg, Analytic Hierarchy Process, Total deformation, Directional deformation

1. Introduction

Prosthetic legs are mainly used to perform leg amputations more easily and sometimes the appearance is similar to a real leg. Different types of legs have been developed in recent days to use for a specific field like running, cycling in sports. Few are designed for normal walking. The selection of materials and load bearing capacity of a leg

determines its usage for any field of application. The behaviour of these legs can be assessed properly by performing finite element analysis by altering the material properties and loads before designing these components. People who have lost their legs due to injury, birth, have the option to use prosthetic legs for performing functional requirements of limbs. The legs developed should be resistant to wear, comfortable, reliable, moisture resistant and high load withstanding ability. When an arm or other extremity is amputated or lost, a prosthetic device, or prosthesis, can play an important role in rehabilitation. For many people, an artificial limb can improve mobility and the ability to manage daily activities, as well as provide the means to stay independent. These characteristics can be achieved by proper selection of materials for manufacturing a prosthetic leg. The main part of a prosthetic leg includes a socket, residual limb and base foot. The materials selected for these parts have to sustain the loads acting on it. Since 1980s there is a significant development in the usage of materials for sockets ranging from wood, leather, and aluminium to plastic. At present carbon fibers are occupying better place to use as a socket material because of its excellent wear, high strength and fatigue characteristics.

2. Description of the Problem

The purpose of a prosthetic leg is to aid individuals who have lost or had limbs amputated due to accidents or diseases, alleviating their suffering and enhancing their mobility. In this study, alternative materials for a prosthetic leg are considered, and using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), priorities are established to select a suitable material. Then, the prosthetic leg was modeled using Solid Works software. Subsequently, various materials and loading conditions were analyzed through simulations using ANSYS software. This approach allows for the customization of the prosthetic leg to meet the specific needs of each user. The comprehensive modeling and analysis conducted aim to ensure the prosthetic leg's effectiveness and usability. Prosthetic legs, or prostheses, can significantly improve the mobility and quality of life for people with leg amputations

2.1 Parts of a Prosthetic leg Limb

This is the main part of the prosthesis. There are two common types that are used for legs.

- Below the knee: When a lower prosthetic leg is attached to an intact upper leg.
- Above the knee: A lower and upper prosthetic leg with a knee.
- The design of it will be dependent on each individual and their preferences.

Feet with Energy Return / Dynamic Response Feet

The basic element of these feet is the design of the keel that simulates a spring moulded carbon fibre plates. This design has better energy response during the toe-off phase (imitating the natural impulse of the foot) by means of the shape and the material of the keel. The foot store and release energy when the individual is walking by absorbing the energy from the keel in the "roll-over" phase of walking. This creates a push off action

Rotator

A device for joining a prosthetic foot to a prosthetic ankle block with limited, resilient rotation there between includes a generally cylindrical adapter or housing secured in the lower end of the ankle block, coaxial with the vertical pivot axis of the foot. An outer spool is secured within the adapter, and an inner spool freely rotates therein on two bearings disposed between the spools and spaced axially there along. A rubber annulus is disposed between the spools intermediate to the bearings, and vulcanized in place to adhere to both spools and form a resilient link there between. A pin extends downward from the outer spool to engage a slot in the foot and limit the rotation thereof.

Pistoning

One of the most obvious losses of suspension is "Pistoning". Pistoning happens when your residual limb lifts out of your socket when you take weight off of it and pushes in when you apply weight. Each step your limb moves up and down in the socket like a piston. This means that every time you lift your leg, there is a delay before your prosthesis begins to move. It also means you must pick your whole leg up that much higher to clear the ground.

Pylon:

Lower limbs tubes or pylons are prosthetics components that are claimed to support loads during walking and other daily tasks activities, i.e., in lower limb amputations, when attached to a socket it replaces the role of the tibia and fibula bones as support structure.

Figure-1: Assembly of prosthetic leg considered for modeling and analysis

3. Modeling and Analysis of Prosthetic leg

All the parts of prosthetic leg shown in figure-1 are modeled using Solid works and analysis has been carried out using ANSYS. Analysis of prosthetic leg has been carried out under different loading conditions such as, walking and running. Different materials have been considered for analysis. While conducting analysis, mechanical performance has been taken into account to predict its effectiveness.

When discussing the mechanical performance of a prosthetic leg, the parameters "total deformation" and "directional deformation" are crucial for understanding how the prosthetic will behave under different conditions and loads. Here's an explanation of each:

3.1 Total Deformation

Total deformation refers to the overall change in shape or size of the prosthetic leg when subjected to forces or loads. It is a measure of how much the entire structure deforms, considering all directions and components of the deformation. In the context of a prosthetic leg, total deformation indicates how much the leg bends, stretches, or compresses when a person walks, runs, or puts weight on it. It provides a comprehensive view of the leg's structural integrity and its ability to maintain its shape under various conditions. It is important from the following aspects:

- **Stability and Support:** Lower total deformation ensures that the prosthetic leg provides adequate support and stability to the user. Excessive deformation can lead to instability, making it difficult for the user to walk or perform daily activities safely.
- **Durability:** Minimizing total deformation helps in prolonging the lifespan of the prosthetic leg. Repeated excessive deformation can lead to material fatigue and eventual failure.
- **Efficiency:** Less deformation can result in more efficient energy transfer, reducing the effort required by the user to move.

3.2 Directional Deformation

Directional deformation focuses on the deformation in a specific direction or along a particular axis. This parameter is crucial for understanding how the prosthetic leg deforms in response to forces applied in different directions, such as vertically, horizontally, or along the length of the leg. For instance, in a prosthetic leg, directional deformation might be analyzed in:

- **Axial direction (along the length of the leg):** How much the leg compresses or elongates.
- **Lateral direction (side to side):** How much the leg bends to the left or right.
- **Anterior-posterior direction (front to back):** How much the leg bends forward or backward.

Understanding directional deformation helps in assessing the stability and performance of the prosthetic leg under various movements and loads. It is particularly important for ensuring that the leg provides proper support and mimics natural limb movements. It is important from the following aspects:

- **Comfort and Fit:** Ensuring minimal and controlled deformation in critical directions can improve the comfort and fit of the prosthetic leg for the user.
- **Safety and Durability:** Analyzing both total and directional deformations helps in designing a leg that can withstand daily activities and avoid failures or excessive wear.
- **Performance:** Understanding how the prosthetic leg deforms under different conditions helps in optimizing its performance for activities like walking, running, or climbing stairs.

By carefully analyzing and optimizing both total and directional deformations, designers and engineers can create prosthetic legs that are more comfortable, durable, and functional for users.

The optimal levels of total deformation and directional deformation for a prosthetic leg depend on the specific design goals and requirements. Here's an analysis of why these parameters should be minimized or optimized rather than simply being more or less:

Balancing the Parameters

- **Material Selection:** Using advanced materials that have high strength-to-weight ratios can help in achieving lower total deformation while allowing for controlled directional deformation.
- **Design Optimization:** Structural design elements such as reinforcement in specific areas and flexibility in others can help in balancing the need for rigidity and flexibility.
- **User Needs:** Individual user requirements and activity levels should be considered. For instance, an athlete might require a prosthetic leg with different deformation characteristics compared to a sedentary individual.

Total deformation should generally be minimized to ensure stability, support, and durability, while directional deformation should be carefully controlled to provide comfort, natural movement, and adaptability. The key is to strike a balance that meets the functional requirements and enhances the user's quality of life.

Four materials have been considered for analysis. They are structural steel, aluminum alloy, carbon fibre and titanium alloy. Using AHP priorities have been established. The modeled prosthetic leg has been subjected to analysis in walking and running conditions. Model of the prosthetic leg and meshed model are portrayed in the figures-2 and figure-3 respectively.

Figure-2

Figure-3

4. Results and discussion

Table-1: Analysis of prosthetic leg in running condition

S No	Material	Total deformation (mm)	Directional deformation (mm)
1	Structural steel	0.0377682	0.010537
2	Titanium alloy	0.050243	0.014049
3	Aluminium alloy	0.043962	0.012293
4	Carbon fibre	0.062083	0.017571

Detailed Discussion

1. Structural Steel

- Total Deformation: 0.0377682 mm
- Directional Deformation: 0.010537 mm

Analysis:

- Structural steel has the lowest total deformation, indicating it deforms the least under load.
- It also has the lowest directional deformation, suggesting it maintains its shape better under specific directional loads.
- This makes structural steel highly stable and durable but at the cost of being heavier than the other materials.

2. Titanium Alloy

- Total Deformation: 0.050243 mm
- Directional Deformation: 0.014049 mm

Analysis:

- Titanium alloy exhibits slightly higher deformation compared to structural steel.
- Its higher strength-to-weight ratio and biocompatibility make it a popular choice despite its higher deformation.
- The trade-off between its lightweight and durability compared to structural steel makes it a suitable option for active users who need a balance of strength and weight.

3. Aluminium Alloy

- Total Deformation: 0.043962 mm
- Directional Deformation: 0.012293 mm

Analysis:

- Aluminum alloy shows higher deformation than structural steel but lower than titanium and carbon fiber.
- It is lightweight, which can enhance user comfort and reduce fatigue.
- The moderate deformation indicates a reasonable balance between strength and weight, making it a cost-effective alternative for prosthetic limbs.

4. Carbon Fiber

- Total Deformation: 0.062083 mm
- Directional Deformation: 0.017571 mm

Analysis:

- Carbon fiber has the highest deformation among the materials tested.
- Despite its higher deformation, carbon fiber is known for its excellent strength-to-weight ratio, making it extremely lightweight.
- The higher deformation suggests that while carbon fiber is strong, it might not be as rigid as the other materials under load, which could affect stability.
- However, the lightweight nature of carbon fiber can significantly benefit users needing a very light prosthetic for ease of movement and comfort.

Inference

- Structural Steel: Best for maximum stability and minimum deformation but is heavier. Suitable for users where weight is not a primary concern but strength and stability are critical.
- Titanium Alloy: Provides a good balance between weight and strength with moderate deformation. Ideal for active users who need durability and biocompatibility.
- Aluminum Alloy: Offers a lightweight option with moderate deformation, making it cost-effective and suitable for users who prioritize comfort and affordability.
- Carbon Fiber: Best for minimal weight, although it has the highest deformation. Suitable for users prioritizing lightweight prosthetics and can handle the higher deformation.

Each material has its advantages and trade-offs. The choice depends on the specific needs, preferences, and activity level of the user.

5. Conclusions

The design and analysis of prosthetic legs represent a critical endeavor in the pursuit of enhancing the quality of life for individuals facing limb loss. This project embarked on a comprehensive journey, beginning with an exploration of the need, importance, advantages, and drawbacks of prosthetic legs. Subsequently, a meticulous design process was undertaken using Solid Works modeling package, followed by a rigorous material selection procedure employing the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). The chosen materials, Aluminium alloy, Titanium alloy, Carbon fibre, and Structural steel, were evaluated based on key mechanical properties, including tensile strength, compressive strength, Young's modulus, and fatigue strength.

The selection of materials for prosthetic leg construction is paramount, as it directly influences the device's performance, durability, and wearer's comfort. Through the application of AHP, it was determined that Titanium alloy emerged as the optimal choice, demonstrating superior mechanical properties compared to alternative materials. This underscores the significance of material science in prosthetic design, where the careful balance of strength, flexibility, and weight is essential to ensure optimal functionality and wearer satisfaction.

The subsequent phase of the project involved the analysis of the prosthetic leg assembly using finite element analysis (FEA) in ANSYS. By inputting the properties of Titanium alloy and Structural steel into the meshed model, the behavior of the prosthetic leg under various loading conditions was studied. The analysis revealed insights into stress distribution, fatigue resistance, and deformation characteristics, providing valuable information for further refinement and optimization of the design.

Future work

It is imperative to acknowledge the ongoing opportunities for innovation and improvement in prosthetic design. Future endeavors may explore advancements in material science, additive manufacturing techniques, and sensor integration to further enhance the functionality and comfort of prosthetic limbs. Additionally, continued collaboration between engineers, medical professionals, and end-users will be essential in driving forward progress and addressing the evolving needs of amputees worldwide.

References

- [1] A. F. Azocar, L. M. Mooney, L. J. Hargrove and E. J. Rouse, "Design and Characterization of an Open-Source Robotic Leg Prosthesis," *2018 7th IEEE International Conference on Biomedical Robotics and Biomechanics (Biorob)*, Enschede, Netherlands, 2018, pp. 111-118, doi: 10.1109/BIOROB.2018.8488057.
- [2] B. E. Lawson, J. Mitchell, D. Truex, A. Shultz, E. Ledoux and M. Goldfarb, "A Robotic Leg Prosthesis: Design, Control, and Implementation," in *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 70-81, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1109/MRA.2014.2360303.
- [3] R. D. Gregg, T. Lenzi, L. J. Hargrove and J. W. Sensinger, "Virtual Constraint Control of a Powered Prosthetic Leg: From Simulation to Experiments With Transfemoral Amputees," in *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 1455-1471, Dec. 2014, doi: 10.1109/TRO.2014.2361937.

- [4] Hargrove, L.J., Young, A.J., Simon, A.M., Fey, N.P., Lipschutz, R.D., Finucane, S.B., Halsne, E.G., Ingraham, K.A. and Kuiken, T.A., 2015. Intuitive control of a powered prosthetic leg during ambulation: a randomized clinical trial. *Jama*, 313(22), pp.2244-2252.
- [5] Andrysek, J., 2010. Lower-limb prosthetic technologies in the developing world: A review of literature from 1994–2010. *Prosthetics and orthotics international*, 34(4), pp.378-398.
- [6] Windrich, M., Grimmer, M., Christ, O., Rinderknecht, S. and Beckerle, P., 2016. Active lower limb prosthetics: a systematic review of design issues and solutions. *Biomedical engineering online*, 15, pp.5-19.
- [7] Esquenazi, A., 2014. Gait analysis in lower-limb amputation and prosthetic rehabilitation. *Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation Clinics*, 25(1), pp.153-167.
- [8] Omkarprasad S. Vaidya and Sushil Kumar, 2006. *European Journal of Operations Research*, 169(1), pp 1-29.